

FLUIDIZED HOT MELT GRANULATION: A PROMISING METHOD**Saranya M.^{1*}, Bhuvaneshwari S., Hassan Ali A., Aravindh I., Ayyanar P., Arshad S.**

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ABSTRACT

Fluidized Hot Melt Granulation is a technology employed in pharmaceutical manufacturing that avoids the use of water and organic solvents through the use of meltable binders which aid in the formation of particles through controlled heat. FHMg is an innovative technique involving meltable binder to agglomerate fluidized dry powders. Fluidized Hot-melt granulation techniques have received enhancing attention due to the significant advantages compared to the other granulation methods. Its advantage lies in its improved heat and mass transfer properties through the combination of granulation through melting and fluidization techniques, making the granules formed homogenous, flowable, and easily compressed. This paper discusses the basics, processes, materials, equipment, and some important variables affecting FHMg such as binder properties, melting temperature and air

flow. FHMg holds great potential in formulating immediate or modified-release drug products, especially those moisture-sensitive, even with challenges like high energy requirements and thermal sensitivity of certain drugs.

KEYWORDS: Granulation, agglomerate, fluidization, meltable binder.**INTRODUCTION**

Granulation results in the formation of large multiparticle structures referred to as granules through the combination of small powder particles. The typical size of pharmaceutical granules, which depend on their intended application, usually ranges from 0.2 to 4.0 mm.^[1] Methods of granulation include high shear granulation, twin screw extrusion, and fluidized

bed granulation. Researchers are currently exploring and developing innovative technologies to overcome the disadvantages of conventional granulation techniques.^[2] An innovative approach used to manufacture pharmaceutical granules for tablets involves fluidized hot melt granulation (FHMG). It has been shown that a number of parameters such as binder composition and quantity, particle size, and air flow rate influence tablet properties significantly.^[3]

One emerging technique is referred to as melt granulation (MG), which employs binders with relatively low melting points (typically 50-80 °C). This is one approach in which high shear mixers, fluid bed granulators, and extruders could be employed. Melttable binders are increasingly preferred due to the several benefits associated with their application compared to other granulation techniques.^[4] Fluidized bed hot melt granulation (FBHMG) technique has been receiving much attention recently in connection with the manufacturing of pharmaceutical powders. One major advantage with the technique is the absence of solvent in the granulation process.

This technique has been applied in the preparation of several formulations such as acetaminophen granules with polyethylene glycol, potassium chloride-loaded white beeswax microcapsules, theophylline granules, chlorpheniramine maleate microparticles with beeswax, and propranolol hydrochloride formulations among others.^[5]

FUNDAMENTALS FOR FLUIDIZED HOT MELT GRANULATION

Due to the capabilities of fluidized bed technology in offering a viable way for continuous operations like coating, drying, and granulation, the technique is usually applied in making tablets. In fluidized bed granulation, the particles are suspended through fluidization using upward air streams following spraying of a binder solution, suspension, or dispersion in a powder bed.

The interactions of the particles when the liquid binder wets them cause formation of liquid bridges, which finally lead to formation of granules. The forces responsible for holding the particles together through the liquid bridges include:

1. Surface tension at the interface
2. Hydrostatic sucking force.^[6]

The variables include primary particle size, fluidizing air velocity, concentration of binder solution, and spray rate, among others. Also, minimizing granule breakage requires special attention considering the manufacturing conditions. It is evident that the effectivity of fluidized bed granulation technology in improving the solubility and dissolution rate of drugs that are poorly water-soluble is known. Granules or agglomerates are formed in this technique when the bridges formed by liquid become stable during drying. Fluidized bed granulation involves the continuous pre-mixing of dry excipients before the particles are wetted and dried. It remains challenging to control fluidized bed granulation technology due to several factors interacting together. When excess spray rate and uneven spray rate lead to attachment and formation of huge lumps, large parts of the bed will be defluidized. This phenomenon is referred to as wet quenching. In contrast, an increase in the minimum fluidization velocity, which is directly proportional to the square of particle diameter, may occur due to particle size increase. The phenomenon of dry quenching occurs when fluidization is hindered due to minimum fluidization velocity becoming larger than the operating velocity.^[7]

ADVANTAGES

1. Elimination of drying process using solvent-free method.
2. Ideal for moisture-sensitive drugs.
3. Improved flow properties and compaction characteristics.
4. More economical in terms of time and cost.
5. Produces more uniform material.
6. Compatible with M manufacturing.^[8,9]

DISADVANTAGES

1. High consumption of energy.
2. The method requires specialized equipment and proper maintenance of the equipment.
3. Heat-sensitive materials cannot be treated with this technique.
4. Thermolabile chemicals were prone to decomposition.^[10,8]

EQUIPMENTS USED

High shear blender

High shear mixers (HSMs) or high shear reactors (HSRs) or also known as rotor-stator mixers and high shear homogenizers operate with extremely high shear rates (up to 20,000 to 100,000 s⁻¹) and rotor tip speed (around 10-50 m/s). These high shear mixers generally

consume greater power compared to normal stirred tanks and generate high energy dissipation near the head of the mixing process. Centrifugal force exerted due to the differential motion between the rotor and the stator, the small separation distances of 100 to 3000 μm between the stator and rotor, is mostly behind such behavior. HSMs have been widely used in industries that require high amounts of energy input in processes such as homogenization, dispersion, emulsification, grinding, dissolution, and cell disruption.^[13]

Twin Screw Excavators

The twin screw excavator is a potential basis for the continuing production of medicinal granules. Properties of granules can be easily regulated owing to the design of the modular screws, thereby giving plenty of flexibility. Porosity of granules can vary greatly depending on the design of the screws. The tensile strength of the tablets made from such granules is also largely dependent on the right selection of screw elements. There exists a direct relationship between granule porosity and the natural logarithm of granule friability.^[14]

Fluidized bed processors

The fluidized bed processors are dependent on effective mixing of particles and uniform dispersion of gases. But one of the issues that occur while scaling fluidized bed processes from lab to commercial scale is avoiding granule breakage, fine loss, and segregation of particles. Moreover, since fluidization phenomenon and its effects are highly scale-dependent, existing approaches tend to limit the optimization of the process without significant experiments at large scales. Particle size distribution, internal design, reactor geometry, and physical properties of the powder influence fluidization phenomena. As a result, complex numerical models that can model the interactions between particles and fluid, including drag forces, particle-to-wall collisions, and three-dimensional interactions between particles, are required for the accurate simulation of fluidized beds.^[15]

CONDITIONS

1. Melting temperatures of the binder substances utilized in hot-melt granulation normally range from 50 to 90 degrees Centigrade.
2. Although hydrophobic binders are preferable for developing modified-release drug delivery formulations, hydrophilic binders are generally employed in the preparation of immediate-release drug formulations.
3. In normal ambient temperature conditions, it is expected that it remains solid.

4. Moreover, to ensure consistent processing in hot-melt granulation, it should have predictable melting behavior.
5. Furthermore, when formulating drugs, it should exhibit compatibility with the other formulation components, including the active pharmaceutical ingredients.^[16,17]

TECHNIQUES

Wetting and nucleation step

During the nucleation step the binder comes into contact with the powder bed and some liquid bridges are formed, leading to the formation of small agglomerates. Two nucleation mechanisms are I. Immersion II. Distribution Immersion Wetting and nucleation step During the nucleation step the binder comes into contact with the powder bed and some liquid bridges are formed, leading to the formation of small agglomerates.^[18]

Spray congealing method

When a medication is dispersed in a liquid medium, the resulting mixture is converted to micro-particles through a technique known as spray congealing, wherein the solution is atomized to form droplets. As soon as the droplets come into contact with air at low temperatures, they solidify rapidly to form solid particles. Typically, one of the three kinds of equipment would be employed for this purpose: two fluid nozzles, airless nozzles, and rotary atomizers.^[17] For this particular technique, a blend of waxes, fatty acids, and glycerides are heated and then sprayed into an air chamber whose temperature is maintained beneath their melting point. Once cooled, the droplets solidify to form particles ranging from 10 to 3000 μm in diameter.^[21]

Coalescence step

It involves nuclei that has residual surface liquid to promote successful fusion of nuclei. The surface liquid imparts plasticity to the nuclei and is essential for enabling the deformation of nuclei surface for coalescence as well as promoting the rounding of granulation.^[19]

Attrition-breakage step

The terms attrition-breakage describe the fragmentation of granules that is consolidated by tray cooling to room temperature without the requirement for tumble drying. Breakage is therefore understood to have a more crucial function in influencing the final qualities.^[18]

Distribution step

A melted binding liquid is distributed into the fine solid particles. The nuclei are formed by the collision between the wetted particles. Generally, small binder droplet size, low binder viscosity, and high shearing force these are the favourable parameters for nucleation by the distribution method.^[20]

Granulation of tumbling melts

The TMG process with the centrifugal fluidizing granulator (CF) was employed for the preparation of solvent free coatings of controlled release beads. Drug-loaded cores (nicotinamide, isoniazide, theophylline and salicylic acid) were preheated to 61-63 °C and then HCO was added to form a layer around them.

Dissolution studies revealed an increase in the rate of release as the solubility of drugs increased. This suggested that diffusion was the mechanism of release as superimposed dissolution profiles gave permeability coefficients which reduced with an increase in drug solubility and did not depend on pH levels.^[22]

PROCESS – PARAMETERS

Process-Related Factor

1). Binder Spray Rate

The particle size can be affected by the rate of droplet generation, which depends highly on the spray rate of the binder. Some of the factors that determine the size of the droplet include atomization pressure and volume, binder viscosity, and the flow rate of the liquid. Larger droplets are usually formed due to high flow rates of liquids, thus creating larger granules.

2). Air Pressure at Atomization

Compressed air is used to atomize the binder solution. Maintaining a uniform ratio of air to liquid ensures that small particles are generated.

3). Air Flow for Fluidization

For ensuring proper fluidization without filter blockage, adequate air flow is required. Attrition of particles along with rapid solvent evaporation due to high air flow can lead to the formation of smaller particles.

4). Temperature of Inlet Process Air

Temperature for input process air depends upon the type of solvent used in the process. While organic solvents require a low temperature range of 50 °C and less than room temperature, aqueous solvents tend to work well within 60–100 °C. Drying capacity of the air being higher can lead to rapid drying of binder before making the required connections while inadequate capacity will cause bed moisture and uncontrolled particle growth.

Equipment Related Factor

1). Shaker / Blow-Back cycle

To prevent any accumulation of fines on the filter causing poor fluidization and thereby affecting process efficiency, a multi-shake filter bag is used in the equipment. The frequency range of shaker used is around 15 to 30 seconds per cycle.

2). Position of nozzle and nozzle height

Granulation of the particles largely depends on the positioning of the spray nozzle. Large particle formation can occur if the nozzle is placed very near the fluidized bed due to overspray. However, the spray can get dried up in the air if the nozzle is placed too high above the bed.

3). Design of Chamber and Container

A proper design of the vessel can help minimize the separation of particles of lighter and heavy fractions. Usually, a cylindrical expansion chamber together with the conical container is employed. The diameter ratio of the distributor plate area and the top of the vessel is maintained at approximately 1:2.

4). Perforated Plate for Air Distributor

Fluidization in the fluid bed is achieved through the velocity of conditioned air, which is supplied through the lower plenum. The more dense products need a higher fluidizing velocity, while the less dense products need a lower velocity. Even distribution of the air throughout the product bed is ensured through special perforated distributor plates that are often made up of 60-325 mesh stainless steel screens.

Formulation related Factor

1). Minimal drug content

The random movement of particles within the fluid bed may result in segregation when using minimal drug contents in the formulation process. This challenge is overcome when the drug content is incorporated into the granulating fluid, which ensures that there is an even distribution of the drug content in the granules.

2). Granulating agent and binders

The attributes of granules such as friability, flowability, bulk density, porosity, and particle size distribution are predominantly influenced by the type, amount, and content of the binding agent. Due to their quick evaporation rate, organic solvents tend to produce smaller granules compared to aqueous solvent systems.^[23]

APPLICATIONS

1. With enhanced compressibility and powder flow properties, the technology facilitates optimal tablet formation and production.
2. Drug release kinetics can be made either sustained or controlled using this technology.
3. This helps patients by providing an effective solution for concealing unpleasant tastes through coating of the medications' particulates.
4. To enhance the physical and chemical stability of vitamins, flavoring substances, and active ingredients, the process is often employed.
5. The technology is particularly beneficial for those materials which are heat- and moisture-sensitive, thereby avoiding the need for organic solvent and thermal drying steps.^[24,25]

CONCLUSION

One such innovation in the field of granulation processes in pharmaceuticals is fluidized hot melt granulation (FHMG), which addresses several limitations of wet granulation and dry granulation methods. Being free from any form of solvent, the process ensures safety, environmental friendliness, and suitability for the formulation of drugs that are sensitive to moisture and heat. The process also enables greater control over factors such as particle size, density, and compressibility, which are necessary for ensuring quality tablet formation. However, the successful application of fluidized hot melt granulation depends on the proper setting of variables such as binder choice, temperature, airflow, and equipment design. Despite challenges such as high energy consumption, complexity, and the risk of thermal

degradation of the active components, ongoing research is constantly working towards making the process more feasible and effective.

In conclusion, FHMG represents an efficient and highly promising technique within modern pharmaceutical manufacturing, especially in cases involving complex drug delivery systems and continuous manufacturing. The expectation is that further investigation of process optimization and scaling up, along with developing novel binder materials, will enhance the technique's effectiveness and practicality.

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